

Deliverable
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP1.3
Workpackage 1

Responsible Partner: 2-AGES, 25-NUIG, 36-INSA

Contributing partners: 7-SZU, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 13-SSI, 14-UT, 20-IP, 23-UoS, 33-NVI, 34-PI-WET

DATA AND PROTOCOL MANAGEMENT PLAN (T3)

Description of the task

The deliverable **D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP1.3** (Data and Protocol Management Plan) was part of the task **JRP15-WP1.3**, which started on M25 and will be finishing on M52. The Supervisory Board of the FED-AMR consortium started to develop a Data and Protocol Management Plan (DPMP) at the Kick-off Meeting (M25) and aimed to have a preliminar DPMP available by M31.

The task leader (Manuela Canica, 36-INSA) attended an online training on August 5th 2020 held by OHEJP WP4 team about the new OHEJP Data Management Plan electronic tool (CDP tool, <https://apps.lisam.com/app>), which aims at facilitating consortium members the generation of their respective DPMPs. This electronic tool, which has been validated by the OHEJP PMT and highly recommended to all DPMP leaders, ensures the harmonization of all DMPs of the consortium.

Description of the deliverable

This deliverable was intended to output a draft of the FED-AMR Protocol and Data Management Plan, which will be ameliorated and regularly updated throughout the whole project duration. Both the task leader (Manuela Caniça, 36-INSA) and the deputy leader (Alexandre de Menezes, 25-NUIG), with support of the WP1 deputy leader (Adriana Cabal, 2-AGES) have already generated a first draft of the FED-AMR DMP using the CDP tool. The content of the PDMP will be adapted and updated throughout the project until its completion in M52, with information provided to the task leader and deputy leader by the different WP leaders.

Due to the COVID-19 response and the recent generation of the mentioned electronic tool (CDP) made available by OHEJP in M32, the due date for this deliverable was postponed from **M27** to **M34**, as indicated in the 9M report.

The FED-AMR PDMP determines which type of data are collected, processed or produced along the project, which techniques and standards are used, whether data and/or protocols will be shared and made publicly available, whether and how they will be made accessible for verification and/or reuse, and how they will be curated and stored (even after the end of the project period). The electronic PDMP is a living document and it will be curated and updated at regular intervals during the FED-AMR project. Furthermore, FED-AMR follows the FAIR principle of Data Management, which ensures that all generated data are findable, accesible, interoperable and re-usable.

Confidentiality of the documents

The current deliverable is public.